

STRATEGIC SUCCESSION PLANNING AND CONTINUITY OF FAMILY BUSINESSES IN SOUTH EAST NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The study examines the relationship between strategic succession planning and continuity of family business in South East Nigeria. The objectives of the study were to: ascertain the extent of relationship between leadership and continuity of family business and examine the extent of relationship between family members commitment and continuity of family business in South East Nigeria. Descriptive survey was adopted. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) versions 16.0 were used. To confirm the significance of the correlation between variables, Pearson correlation analysis was performed. The study revealed that The study revealed that leadership had positive relationship with survival of family business in South East Nigeria ($r=0.161$, $p < 0.000 < 0.05$) and The study revealed that family members' commitment had positive relationship with survival of family business in South East, Nigeria ($r = 0.400$, $p < 0.000 < 0.05$). The study concluded that strategic succession planning had positive relationship with continuity of family businesses in South East, Nigeria. The following recommendations were made the leadership of family businesses should continue to arrange for successor training and setting a retirement date every member of the family can know when or time to handover the businesses to the next person. The family commitment plan should be developed and attached to the business strategic plan. So family can explore its values, family businesses philosophy and family vision to assess its commitment to the business for developing family members for management and leadership roles.*

Keywords: strategic succession planning, continuity of family businesses, leadership, family members commitment, South East Nigeria, successor training, retirement date, family commitment plan, family business philosophy

INTRODUCTION

A family business may be defined as any business in which two or more family members are involved and the majority of ownership or control lies within a family (Randel, Kets-de-Vries and Florent-Treacy, 2019). In some countries, many of the largest publicly listed firms are family-owned. A firm is said to be family-owned if a person is the controlling shareholder; that is, a person (rather than a state, corporation, management trust, or mutual fund) can garner enough shares to assure at least 20% of the voting rights and the highest percentage of voting rights in comparison to other shareholders (Chakrabarty, 2009).

In a family business, two or more members within the management team are drawn from the owning family. Family businesses may also be managed by individuals who are not members of the family (Alderson, 2011). However, a broad general definition of the family firm is one where a family owns enough of the equity to be able to exert control over strategy and is involved in top management positions. In Nigeria, many businesses that

are now public companies were once family businesses. The founder of a business is a major source of knowledge and expertise and the owner's social networks represent important intangible assets for the company.

Family business succession is the process of transitioning the management and the ownership of the business to the next generation of family members (Walsh, 2016). However, a broad general definition of the family firm is one where a family owns enough of the equity to be able to exert control over strategy *and* is involved in top management positions (Walsh, 2016). Rodrigo (2013) defines succession planning as the process of identifying and preparing suitable employees through mentoring, training and job rotation, to replace key players within an organization as those key players leave their positions for whatever reasons such as retirement, advancement and attrition.

The Family Owned Businesses (FOB) in Nigeria are mostly small and Medium Enterprises (SMES) (Obadan and Ohioenoya, 2013; Onuoha, 2015). They create employment opportunities, have and capacity to reduce poverty, inequality and social vices, are catalysts of innovation, inventions and creativity; stimulate indigenous entrepreneurship; link up the various sectors and sub-sectors of the economy; pay taxes which enable governments to provide basic amenities; and contribute to regional activities and cooperation (Onuoha, 2013).

The future prosperity of both family and business depend upon how well understanding and contacts are passed on and how far these are trusted and valued by the next generation (Lee, Lim and Lim, 2013). Successfully transferring family businesses to the next generation raises complex and emotional problems. Planning for the transition cannot start too early, and the whole process needs to be very carefully managed. But many entrepreneurs are reluctant to face up to the thought of giving up control, and succession is one of the main causes of divisions and tensions that can damage family life and undermine business performance.

The most significant challenge faced by family businesses is survival from one generation to the next. Optimizing the likelihood of business survival requires family businesses to lay forth a workable plan in securing next generation involvement. Continuity of these core business values is essential for upholding a long standing business image which both external and internal stakeholders will recognize. Management and ownership succession are two critical factors on which all other business activities revolve (Onuoha, 2013). Based on above background of the study, the study seems to examine the relationship between strategic succession planning and continuity of family businesses in South East Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Family businesses make a big cumulative contribution to jobs and exports. A lot of big companies these days are eager to copy the speed of decisions and the entrepreneurial flair that family business ownership and control are thought to confer. However, family businesses nowadays face the frightening challenge of changing leaders at a time of rapid technological change and increased competitive forces from globalization.

Most family businesses appear to struggle with leadership succession between different generations of family members. The challenge for any business is continuity as one generation plans for retirement or it may come as a surprise resignation from a key employee or an employee is lost due to death or long term disability.

The biggest problem with the family owned business may be attributed to lack of strategic succession planning. Indeed, poorly planned successions are among the biggest value-destroying events for family businesses. Families hesitate to plan succession because they are uncertain how the interests, choices, and decisions of different family members will play out over years or decades. Growth also may be a dilemma if some relatives are reluctant to plough profits back into the business

Without the family's commitment, there can be no parallel planning process. If the family cannot develop a shared commitment to invest and participate in the business, then it may be time to sell or liquidate. Despite these challenges, it is pertinent to examine the effects of strategic succession planning on the continuity of family businesses in south eastern states of Nigeria and finding solution to it would be rewarding.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to examine strategic succession planning and continuity of Family Businesses (FB) in South East Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of the study were:

- i. To ascertain the extent of relationship between leadership and continuity of family businesses in South East Nigeria.
- ii. To examine the extent of relationship between family members commitment and continuity of family businesses in South East Nigeria.

However, the organization of the study was captured under key subheadings such as review of related literature, methodology, testing of hypotheses and findings, conclusion and recommendations.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Family Businesses

A family business is a commercial organization in which family exercises control over business in the form of ownership or in the form of management of the firm where family members are employed on key positions (Ghadoliya; 2020). They are closely identified with the firm through leadership or ownership. In a family business, two or more members within the management team are drawn from the owning family. Family businesses may also be managed by individuals who are not members of the family. However, family members are often involved in the operations of their family business in some capacity and, in smaller companies, usually one or more family members are the senior officers and managers (Randel, *et al*, 2016).

Succession Planning

Succession planning involves the identification and development of potential successors in an organization. It is referred to as the process of pinpointing key needs for leadership and intellectual talent throughout the organization over time and preparing individuals for present and future work responsibilities. In a family business succession planning involves: strategic planning, financial planning, estate planning, and human resources planning. This planning prepares for future critical vacancies of management positions by forecasting the talent necessary for these roles to provide the groundwork and understanding of the characteristics needed to maintain a company's strategic plan.

Strategic Succession Business Planning

Poutziouris (2010) defines strategic planning as the processes used to plan for the long-term performance of an organization. It creates insights into the company and its environment. Strategic successive planning centering on both business and family goals is vital to successful family businesses. In fact, planning may be more crucial to family businesses than to other types of business entities, because in many cases families have a majority of their assets tied up in the business. Since much conflict arises due to a disparity between family and business goals, planning is required to align these goals and formulate a strategy for reaching them. The ideal plan will allow the company to balance family and business needs to everyone's advantage.

Leadership

Western (2013) opines that Leadership is a practical skill, encompasses the ability of an individual, group or organization to "lead", influence or guide other individuals, members, teams, or entire organizations. Although continuity of leadership is a key strength in businesses, The long physical presence of a founder in a business, whether running the business directly or not, enables the articulation and dissemination of a consistent vision and strategy for the business. One remarkable aspect of successful family business continuity is a founder's ability to embed strong core values and a clear vision, while also developing the managerial skills of key leaders, something not all founders are able to do. The viability of any business succession is inextricably linked to the organization's preparedness in thoughtfully addressing leadership transition and sustainability long before the business is faced with this reality. Collins (2011) outlines the characteristic of a great leader is one who sets up the company to succeed after the founder is gone.

Family Commitment

Commitment to work is defined as the level of enthusiasm an individual has towards his/her tasks assigned at a workplace. It is the feeling of responsibility that an individual has towards the goals, mission, and vision of the organization he/she is working with. The family's commitment is the foundation for creating unity of purpose and maintaining family harmony. The format, or even the content, of these actions is not as important as the process for developing them. Family Commitment is a priority discussion for the family because it supports the development of the shared future vision and the family enterprise continuity plan. Simply, a family that plans its future together can build stronger family relationships and new opportunities for family participation and achievement (Dauda, 2013).

Business Growth

Business growth is a incident that occurs when business owners, employees and outside factors influence the success of a company. Growing a business takes planning and concentrated efforts. Growth means increasing sales, assets, net profits and a chance to take advantage of the experience curve to reduce the per unit cost of products sold and thereby increasing profits (Sumari; 2013). A business grows when it expands a customer base, increases revenue or produces more products. Growth is the goal of most businesses and is the reason behind many decisions that affect the daily workings of a company both internally and externally. Business growth is impacted by consumer trends, market opportunities and decisions made by company leadership.

Business Survival

Business survival refers to keeping the **business** operating for a certain amount of time, especially when some crisis situation comes. Survival may be an important objective, if a business is being threatened by a takeover from a larger more established business. The main objective for the management of the enterprise will be to persuade the owners (shareholders) not to sell their shares to the person or company bidding for them. When trading of goods and services becomes difficult because of recession or lack of the market, individual businesses or industries will face difficulties, or even get out of business. So, survival during difficult times becomes a main objective.

Theoretical Framework

Relay Succession Planning Model of theory was adopted in this study. It was developed by Santorin in (2004) came up with the “Relay Succession Planning” This model says that the responsibility of the designation that is about to be vacant should be passed to the successor over a long period of time. The successor will be exposed to the corporate challenges in the pre-succession phase under the guidance of the person who is designated at the soon to be vacant position and hence he/she is tested at the period of his/her training under the predecessor. Relay Succession Planning Model allows the organization to have time for selection, training, assessment, grooming of the successor and hence helps in creating a transition timetable because an heir who is apparent is selected a few years before the person at the key position is about to retire. The successor then works with the soon to be predecessor. And therefore the successor performs better because he/she is already tried in decisiveness and crisis management.

Empirical Review

In related study of Onyeukwu & Jekelle (2019) investigated leadership succession and sustainability of small family-owned businesses in Anambra, South East Nigeria. The study employed the survey research design. The findings revealed that, mentoring and human capital development has significant influence on sustainability of small family owned businesses.

Similarly Sami & Paul-Laurent (2019) investigated family members’ commitment to the firm and family business continuity: investigating the mediating role of family-to-firm identity fit and emotional attachment. The findings show that family members' commitment to the firm is positively related to the owning family's influence on the firm.

Maintain previous authors point of view, Westhuizen & Andrea (2014) investigated correlation between leadership practices and business performance amongst first and second generation owners of family firms in South Africa. The findings indicate that positive significant correlations exist between the occurrence of leadership practices and business performance for first generation leaders of the selected family businesses, but limited correlations exist between the variables for the second generation leaders.

In relationship with preview author ideals, Maguta (2016) examined the effects of succession planning practices on the performance of (NGOs) in Kenya. The study identified succession planning as the persistent concern for (NGOs) pursuing performance sustainability.

Jose (2007) investigated succession in family business in Canada. The study focused on succession process in Molson family business. The study argued that it is only when succession plan is effective, that is only when conflict could be avoided in among the family members engaged in succession.

Esuh, Mohd, and Adebayo (2011) explored and examined succession in relation to family business continuity in Nigeria and thus, offered a conceptual framework on succession in relation to family business continuity. The study proposed founder, successor and environment will jointly affect family business continuity and that true succession will mediate the relationship between founder, successor and environment, and family business continuity.

Zahrani¹, Nikmaram and Latifi (2014) conducted a study to investigate the impact of family business characteristics on successor planning process in such businesses in Tehran industrial towns in Iran. The findings indicated that there is a positive and significant relationship between business family characteristics especially the tendency of trusted people to succeeding and successor planning.

Salama (2014) conducted an empirical study on the relationship between succession planning practices and employee retention in large media houses in Kenya. The findings also suggest that career management is critical as majority of the employees feel that there are no clear career paths and if they exist, they are too narrow.

Maguta (2016) examined the effects of succession planning practices on the performance of (NGOs) in Kenya. Conclusively, the study identified succession planning as the persistent concern for (NGOs) pursuing performance sustainability. There was an existing gap between conventional management of (NGOs) in Nairobi and the adoption of succession planning practices.

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey design was utilized for the study. Descriptive research is concerned with the description of data and characteristics about a population. The data for the study was two kinds; primary and secondary data. The population of the study consisted of selected medium and large scale enterprises located in south east Nigeria that are family-owned business. The total population of the study was five thousand, two hundred and forty-six (5,246). Sample size was determined using Freund and Williams (1986) statistical sampling formula was applied to obtain the sample size from the population. Therefore, a total number of three hundred and fifty-eight (358) respondents were used for the study as sample size determination. The study used strata to be included from each of the stratum. The instrument for data collection was utilized for the study and structured questionnaire was adopted the respondents. The questionnaire was structured in line with the variables of the study already stated in the hypotheses. The likert-type scale or category was adopted for analysis, namely: strongly agree; (SA); Agree (A); Undecided (UD); Disagree (DA); and Strongly Disagree (SD). Each level is assigned a number ranging from 5 (SA) to 1 (SD). Qualitative data was analyzed descriptively. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) versions 16.0 were used. The data collected with regards to each of the questions were also analyzed using in tables, frequencies, percentages, mean, and standard deviation and ANOVA.

Data Presentation and Analyses

In this chapter four efforts were made to present and analyze the data gathered; which were guided by the research questions already stated in chapter one. The data collected with regards to each of the questions were analyzed using in tables, frequencies, percentages, mean, and standard deviation and ANOVA.

Test of Hypotheses

In this section, mean responses from 3.00 and above were accepted as relationship between leadership and family members' commitment on continuity of family businesses in South East, Nigeria while mean response below 3.00 were rejected.

- i. Leadership has no positive relationship with continuity of family businesses in South East Nigeria.
- ii. Family member commitment has no positive relationship with continuity of family businesses in South East Nigeria.

Table 4.1 Spearman’s Correlation Coefficients among Research Variables

		Survival of the Business	Commitment	Leadership
Succession planning	1			
growth	0.066	1		
Commitment	0.433	0.161	1	
Leadership	0.626	0.286	0.400	1

All coefficients are significant in 95% confidence level.

Spearman’s correlation coefficient directs the positive or negative aspect of the result. But in family member commitment and survival of family business it had positive relationship with coefficient of 0.161. Table 4.1 outlines the results of Spearman’s correlation test between family member commitment and survival of family business. Coefficient of correlation propensity of leadership successor to take over has the most amounts among all coefficients (0.400) and is higher than the average. In general, this study shows that all independent variables had positive with dependent variable.

Summary of Findings

1. The study revealed that leadership had positive relationship with continuity of family businesses in South East Nigeria ($r=0.161$, $p_v 0.000 < 0.05$).
2. The study revealed that family members’ commitment had positive relationship with continuity of family businesses in South East, Nigeria ($r = 0.400$, $p_v 0.000 < 0.05$).

Conclusion

The study concluded that poor or lack of management of succession planning can pose great challenges in the continuity of family businesses. A family business owned and managed by a family will produce lifetime work relationships. For this reason, family must explore its values, family business philosophy and family vision to assess its commitment to the business for developing family members for management and leadership roles. Therefore, the study conclude that leadership had positive relationship with continuity of family businesses in South East Nigeria and family members’ commitment had positive relationship with continuity of family businesses in South East, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and results of this study the following recommendations were made.

- i. Preparing a Succession Plan, leadership should continue to arrange for successor training and setting a retirement date. So that they will make position available to upcoming once.
- ii. Family commitment plan should be developed and attached to the business strategic plan. The family must explore its values, family business philosophy and family vision to assess its commitment to the business for developing family members for management and leadership roles.

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